

INTERLAMINAR SHEAR REINFORCEMENT OF UNIDIRECTIONAL AEROSPACE LAMINATES WITH RADIALLY ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBES

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ABSTRACT

Leveraging previous developments of woven fuzzy carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates [1], radially-aligned CNTs were grown on aerospace grade unidirectional carbon fabrics to realize possible mechanical and electrical property improvements. To increase any matrix reinforcement effects and the fractional fill of CNTs in the weak interlaminar regions, vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) was used to manufacture UD fuzzy CFRP laminates that have low crimp and interlaminar distances. UD fuzzy CFRP and control laminates made from as-received sized CFs and thermally-desized CFs (UD sized CFRP and UD desized CFRP respectively) were manufactured with interlaminar distances and laminate quality assessed through X-ray microcomputed tomography (μ CT). Scanning electron microscopy reveals conformal CNT growth around CFs and complements recent thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) to indicate the removal of the polymeric sizing layer on CFs and the thermoplastic weft (that holds the tows together) during CVD processing. Consequent matrix interface changes as well as process bounds for ensuring ply handling for lamination are informed. Further, as an improvement over past woven fuzzy CFRP work, short-beam shear (SBS) testing data of UD fuzzy CFRP are presented, showing retention of interlaminar shear strength (ILSS). This work introduces a suitable hierarchical UD composite fabrication and testing platform for future CNT growth uniformity and length optimizations to isolate and characterize interlaminar property enhancements.

1 INTRODUCTION

Hierarchical nanoengineered composites have the potential to enhance the mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced composites and add multifunctionality into mass-efficient vehicle structures. Particularly, the incorporation of nanoreinforcement into composites through the circumferential growth of radially aligned carbon nanotubes (a-CNTs) onto microfibers has demonstrated improvements in interlaminar fracture toughness, interlaminar shear strengths, and electrical/thermal conductivities of alumina fiber composites [2]. However, the implementation of this “fuzzy fiber” reinforced plastic (FFRP) architecture onto carbon fibers (CFs) desired for high-performance applications, has resulted in CF strength loss, which compromises in-plane strengths for through-thickness property improvements [3].

We recently demonstrate a method for high-yield growth of CNTs on carbon fabrics to enhance interlaminar properties while maintaining CF strengths [4]. Using a low temperature chemical vapor deposition (CVD) process and a scalable catalyst deposition approach onto filaments, CNTs were directly grown on woven carbon fabrics and found to have preserved tensile strengths as compared to as-received sized CFs and desized CFs. Moreover, these woven fuzzy CF plies were fabricated into laminates for short beam shear testing, resulting in decreased interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) as compared with control CFRPs made from as-received CFs (woven sized CFRP). This result was

attributed to the thermally induced alteration of the polymeric sizing on the carbon fabric, which decreases fiber-matrix interfacial strength [5]. However, woven fuzzy CFRPs exhibited slightly higher ILSS values compared to controls made from as-received sized CFs that had been subjected to the same CVD environment as that used for CNT growth. To further study this enhancement, recent efforts have focused on increasing the fractional fill of CNTs in the interlaminar region by reducing interlaminar distances. Consequently, successful migration of CNT growth onto unidirectional (UD) aerospace carbon fabrics with lower crimp and resultant composites are presented here.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Figure 1. UD carbon fabrics were dipcoated with the support of porous mesh sheets to prevent surface tension induced distortion (a), supported on quartz slides to prevent tow separation up thermoplastic weft transformation (b), and infused with epoxy resin to form UD CFRP laminates (c).

2.1 Direct CNT growth on UD CF Fabrics

Leveraging the catalyst deposition and low temperature CVD previously shown [1], CNTs were grown directly on dry as-received UD TohoTenax HTA45[6] carbon fabrics that were cut into 20 X 64 mm swatches. These swatches were dip-coated in catalyst solutions with the assistance of permeable mesh sheets (Figure 1a) to prevent fabric distortion induced by catalyst solution surface tension. Dipcoated samples were left to dry in ambient for 5 hours on the permeable mesh sheets before being separated for CVD processing.

To prevent tow separation from thermally induced transformations of the thermoplastic weft at growth temperatures, samples were placed flat on quartz slides during CVD processing (Figure 1b). These dip-coated carbon fabrics were then inserted into a tube furnace (22-mm inner diameter, 25-mm outer diameter, 30-cm heated section of the furnace) for thermal chemical vapor deposition processing to grow CNTs using a nominal $\text{CO}_2/\text{C}_2\text{H}_2$ oxidative dehydrogenation reaction: After flushing with Ar at 750 sccm for 2 minutes, the tube furnace was ramped to the growth temperature setpoint (nominally 480 ± 1 °C) while flowing a H_2 rich mixture of 400 sccms of H_2 and 100 sccms of Ar, which creates a hydrogen-rich environment that initiates the catalyst reduction phase. Both Ar and H_2 flow were shut off upon reaching 480 °C (or at the growth temperature setpoint), and 16.7 sccms of CO_2 and 167 sccms of 10 % C_2H_2 in Ar were introduced to initiate CNT growth. The standard growth time was 15 min, after which, both gases were turned off and the furnace cooled to ambient temperature under Ar flow for sample extraction. Note that the 480 °C growth temperature was set to be below the threshold

temperature for fiber strength degradation found from previous work [7]. CNT morphologies were observed under the JEOL 6010LA scanning electron microscope (SEM) at 15 kV and without any gold sputtering since the fibers and CNTs were conductive.

2.2 UD CF Controls and Pretreatments

Dry swatches of UD CFs were processed as outlined in Table 1:

Sample Designation	Dip-coated in catalyst solution	Temperature of furnace	Duration (min)	CO ₂ /C ₂ H ₂ /Ar gas flow ratio during growth (sccm)
UD sized CFs	No	N/A	N/A	No CVD
UD fuzzy CFs	Yes	480 °C	15	17/17/150
UD CVD Processed Sized CFs	No	480 °C	15	17/17/150
Thermally Desized UD CFs	No	400 °C	2	0/0/200

Table 1: Unidirectional carbon fabric processing summary.

2.3 UD Fuzzy CFRP Fabrication and Testing

Dry UD fabrics (fuzzy, as-received sized, and thermally desized) were laminated with Hexcel RTM6 low viscosity aerospace resin through vacuum-assisted resin infusion (VARI) in preparation for SBS testing. These laminates consist of twelve 0° plies with the middle eight plies replaced with UD fuzzy carbon fabrics, and desized carbon fabrics for UD fuzzy CFRP and UD desized CFRP specimens respectively, since the middle plies encounter highest shear during testing. Dry fabrics were stacked between two glass plates separated by spacers, bagged, placed inside an oven, heated to 150 °C for 10 min. to remove moisture, and connected to the resin and vacuum sources at opposite ends. Once the oven had reached 90 °C, the resin was slowly infused through the dry fabrics. After full infusion, the sample was cured at 160 °C for 75 minutes and then 180 °C for 120 minutes. Desired laminate thickness and thus volume fraction was controlled through the thickness of the spacer between the glass plates.

Interlaminar shear strengths were tested in accordance with ASTM D2344, with a support span of 8.8 mm, roller nose diameter of 6 mm, support roller diameter of 3 mm, and a loading nose displacement speed of 1mm/min. Laminates were cut into 4.4 mm x 13.2 mm samples and painted with a base coat of white paint before being speckled with black paint for digital image correlation of the sides of the specimen. Images were acquired at 4 Hz during testing, which were then input into Vic2D software for strain mapping outputs. These maps were used to help identify failure initiation regions and confirm interlaminar shear failure sites.

2.4 X-ray micro-computed tomography

X-ray μ CT (Zeiss Xradia 520 Versa 3D X-ray Microscope) was used to assess void content and to measure interlaminar spacings prior to SBS testing with ~6- μ m-resolution.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2. Scanning electron micrograph of radially aligned CNTs successfully grown directly on UD carbon fabrics imaged after growth processing in Figure 1b.

SEM analysis shows successful and conformal CNT growth on UD CF fabrics with lengths ranging from 1-2 μm (Figure 2). It is noted that patches of growth were observed, with nonuniform CNT coverage through the thickness of the specimen. Additionally, the thermoplastic weft was observed to flow and undergo thermal transformation at elevated temperatures, resulting in local changes to the gas environment that may inhibit CNT growth in adjacent regions. Without performing the growth optimization that is beyond the scope of this study, the majority of the CNT growth is observed on the surface of the fabric, which is of primary interest for interlaminar reinforcement. In addition, the thermoplastic weft in the UD fuzzy CF fabrics was observed to remain such that the plies can still be handled for layup.

Heat-treated control fibers were also observed to undergo different degrees of thermoplastic transformation: UD desized fabrics were found to retain enough thermoplastic weft to keep the tow consolidated and be able to be handled for further processing for lamination. However, CVD-processed sized CFs resulted in full weft removal such that tows were no longer held together. Fibers were separated from the swatch of fabric upon the completion of the heating, and were thus unable to be removed as a ply for lamination and short-beam shear testing. This observation is consistent with previously reported TGA data of these UD fabric controls [8]. When ramped from 0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, desized fibers show a single mass loss event, corresponding to sizing removal, while the CVD processed sized fibers showed two, indicating both sizing and thermoplastic weft removal. Although CVD process sized fibers undergo the same heating and chemical environment in the tube furnace as the fuzzy CF fabrics, the weft retention in the latter suggests that the presence of catalysts or the CNT growth reaction may be inhibiting the weft degradation. This result is advantageous for further scale up of the CVD processing onto larger are or continuous growth methods.

All three types of fabrics infused with RTM6 resin were found to successfully yield laminates that were 2.2 mm thick and reach the targeted carbon fiber volume fraction of 60%. Cross-sectional views from of X-ray micro-CT scan shows that CNT fill-fraction was successfully achieved through decreased interlaminar distances ($< 15 \mu\text{m}$) as compared with previous woven fuzzy CFRPs, which resulted in plies being over $50 \mu\text{m}$ apart due to the fiber crimp (**Figure 3**). Additionally, no detectable void content was observed.

Figure 3. X-ray micro-computed tomography of a representative sized UD CFRP and Woven CFRP SBS specimens showing cross-sectional views to assess interlaminar spacing and laminate quality.

Figure 4 shows the SBS testing results of both the UD CFRP specimens (5 UD sized, 3 UD desized, and 3 UD fuzzy CFRPs) and previously tested woven controls (5 woven sized CFRP and 5 woven desized) for reference [5]. Woven as-received sized CFs that were infused with RTM6 (woven sized CFRP) with 50% volume fraction were observed to fail abruptly and reach test end with an immediate load drop after the initial load peak. Woven desized CFs that were infused with RTM6 (woven desized CFRP) samples resulted in a lower initial load peak, but a tougher response to failure, and in some cases never showing a 30% load drop throughout the test until crosshead travel limits were reached. It was subsequently found that these ILSS values correlated with the fiber-matrix interfacial shear strength (IFSS) for woven CFRPs. Given that CNT growth on as-received sized CFs resulted in sizing transformation/removal, the resultant lower IFSS complicates the direct measurement of interlaminar reinforcement from CNTs between woven plies.

Here, a different trend is observed for UD CFRP specimens: all SBS tested specimens were observed to fail abruptly in the same manner and attain higher ILSS values as expected for UD fabrics with lower crimp and laminated at higher fiber volume fractions. In contrast to the woven case, the UD desized CFRP was observed to result in same ILSS values as UD sized CFRP, which suggests that the ILSS of UD laminates do not correlate with the fiber-matrix IFSS changes (likely due to possible failure initiation type differences). As a result, the UD composites here are advantageous for averting the complications that arise from sizing transformations/removal and can thus be a suitable platform on which to measure through-thickness reinforcement that CNTs may provide. In fact, UD fuzzy CFRP specimens also do not have a decrease in ILSS as exhibited by the woven CFRP case, but instead display retained ILSS values from that of the UD CFRP controls. The UD composite platform is thus a suitable platform for decoupling the sensitivity towards fiber-matrix interface changes and allows for possible quantification of matrix reinforcement from CNTs. It is expected that the non-uniformity of the CNT coverage contributes to the lack of significant improvements here, and thus follow-on work with process tuning for uniform growth on the surface of the UD fabrics and through the thickness will result in statistically significant gains in interlaminar properties.

Figure 4. SBS interlaminar shear strengths calculated from the initial peak load for woven sized CFRP, woven desized CFRP, UD sized CFRP, UD desized CFRP, and UD fuzzy CFRP. The vertical whiskers represent the minimum and maximum data points, whereas the shaded rectangular box ends represent the 1st and 3rd quartiles. The band inside the box displays the median value, and the diamond marker represents the mean.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Direct CNT growth was successfully shown on aerospace grade UD carbon fabrics using a catalyst dipcoating method and low temperature chemical vapor deposition process that preserves fiber strengths. CNT-coated fabrics were infused with low viscosity resin to result in UD fuzzy CFRPs that exhibit lower fiber crimp and interlaminar distances as measured through X-ray microCT, thereby increasing the fraction of the interlaminar region that is filled with CNTs. Short beam shear testing results of UD CFRPs fabricated from as-received sized CFs and desized CFs reveal ILSS values that are within range of each other, and suggest that UD composites are effective in decoupling the effect of fiber-matrix interface changes on ILSS demonstrated previously on woven CFRPs. Moreover, fuzzy CFRP retain ILSS as compared with UD sized CFRP control despite CVD-induced microfibrer sizing transformations during CNT growth. Taken together, this method of testing and fabricating UD fuzzy CFRP enables a platform for quantifying interlaminar mechanical performance enhancements offered through radially-aligned CNTs, and spurs follow-on work for optimizing CNT growth uniformity and lengths.

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